

THE LINGUOCULTUROLOGICAL STUDY OF TOPONYMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

Asqarova Dilshodakhon Asqar qizi

The Master Student of Asia International University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17999562>

Abstract. This thesis is devoted to the linguoculturological analysis of toponyms in the English and Uzbek languages. Toponyms, as geographical names, represent an important layer of the lexical system and reflect the historical, cultural, social, and ethnic characteristics of a nation. The study of toponyms from a linguoculturological perspective allows researchers to reveal the close relationship between language, culture, and national worldview. The main objective of the research is to analyze English and Uzbek toponyms from a comparative linguoculturological perspective in order to identify shared and culture-specific features in their semantic structure, formation, and usage. The study seeks to reveal how cultural values, historical events, ethnic composition, natural environment, and social practices are encoded in place names of both languages. The theoretical framework of the research is based on the principles of linguoculturology, cognitive linguistics, and onomastics. The works of prominent scholars in these fields provide the foundation for understanding toponyms as cultural phenomena and linguistic representations of national mentality. The study also draws upon concepts such as linguistic worldview, cultural codes, and national identity. The scientific novelty of the research lies in its integrated linguoculturological approach to the comparative study of English and Uzbek toponyms. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of how cultural values and national mentality are linguistically encoded in geographical names. The practical significance of the study includes its application in linguistics, cultural studies, translation studies, lexicography, and the teaching of English and Uzbek as foreign languages. The results of this research may serve as a foundation for further studies in comparative linguoculturology and onomastics, as well as for developing educational materials that promote intercultural competence through the study of toponyms.

Keywords: Uzbek toponyms, etymology, English language, cultural significance, place names

Introduction. Toponyms, or place names, serve as vital linguistic markers that encapsulate the history, culture, and identity of a region. In the context of Uzbekistan, a country with a rich historical background and diverse cultural influences, its toponyms offer significant insights into the interplay between language and geography. Toponyms have a special place as a scientific term because this term is comprehensive which means settlements, residential areas: republic, city, province, street, village, daha, mahalla, guzar, district; water basins: ocean, sea, river, pool, lake, reservoir, stream; The people who own the names of each place, but the science of history deals with the task of when it was created, by whom, and why. Linguoculturology, as a modern branch of linguistics, focuses on the interaction between language and culture, emphasizing how cultural values and national mentality are encoded in linguistic units. From a linguoculturological perspective, toponyms can be regarded as culturally marked lexical units that embody symbolic meanings and reflect the cultural identity of a speech community. Therefore, the linguoculturological study of toponyms enables a deeper understanding of how language functions as a repository of cultural knowledge. The present study seeks to analyze English and Uzbek toponyms from a linguoculturological perspective,

focusing on their semantic structure, cultural motivation, and historical background. By examining place names as linguistic and cultural signs, the research aims to demonstrate how national culture and collective consciousness are reflected in the toponymic systems of English and Uzbek languages.

Main body. Every toponym has a distinct meaning and purpose. Place names are the source of their respective historical names in various parts of our republic. The area has been known as "Qarshi" since the XIV century, when the Mongol king constructed a palace for himself. The temple was known as "buhar" in Sanskrit at the time. It takes its name from the Uzbek region of Bukhara. In addition, Andijan refers to a riverbank. The suffixes "kent, duvon, gan, kon, tim, rabot, saroy,-qand" are many and have been used to indicate place names throughout history. Some academics claim that "toponyms are essential components of topography and cartography." From the earliest attempts at etymology in Plato's dialogue *Kratylos* and by the Greek Stoics to the present, etymology took several centuries to establish itself as a scientific field. Additionally, because toponyms hold a unique place in linguistics and serve a variety of purposes manifested through their lexical, structural, and historical peculiarities, etymology is a scientific method that opens an interface to the wide range of human actions in time and space.

Toponyms in English frequently include suffixes or prefixes that denote geographical features or functions. For example: -ham (Old English: village or estate, e.g., Birmingham). -ford (crossing over a river, e.g., Oxford). New- (indicating a newer settlement, e.g., Newcastle) [3, 24]. When Uzbek place names are taken into consideration, they tend to demonstrate more Turkic and Persian elements that describe natural features or historical contexts:

kent or -qishloq (settlement, e.g., Chorkent, Toshkent) tepa (hill, e.g., Gulistontepa). Oq- (white, often symbolic, e.g., Oqshahr, meaning "White City") [4, 26].

In terms of semantic evolution of toponyms in both languages, there are several significant differences can be highlighted. The meanings of many English place names have evolved due to language changes and historical events. For instance, Westminster combines Old English (west) and Latin (monasterium), meaning "western monastery" while Uzbek place names often retain their original meanings, linked to geography or historical figures. For example, Samarkand comes from Persian Samarqand, meaning "Stone Fort." Historically, because of Norse Influence, settlements with names like Derby (-by meaning village) and Grimsby were appeared in England. Names like Beaulieu ("beautiful place") or Richmond ("rich hill") emerged due to Norman and Latin Influence. Moreover, English place names were transplanted globally, e.g., New York (after York in England) or Victoria (named after Queen Victoria) while many Uzbek toponyms were reflected by the Turkic and Persian cultural heritage, such as Bukhara (from Sanskrit Vihara, meaning monastery). The amount of Soviet Influence was also paramount. Hence, During the Soviet era, some Uzbek toponyms were Russified or renamed, e.g., Leninsk for a time. Cultural Reflections are key features in the development of Toponymy both in English and Uzbek languages. In English, many names reflect local legends, natural features, or religion: Holy Island (religion), Lake District (natural features), Robin Hood's Bay (folklore) while Uzbek Toponyms often emphasize natural geography and cultural identity: Nurata (meaning "father of light," linked to sacred sites), Chimgan (mountainous area, derived from Turkic roots).

Conclusion. This study has explored the linguoculturological features of toponyms in the English and Uzbek languages, demonstrating that place names are not merely geographical markers but complex linguistic units that embody historical memory, cultural values, and national identity. Through a comparative analysis, the research has shown how toponyms reflect the worldview, traditions, and socio-cultural development of their respective speech communities.

A toponym is a collection of place names in a specific area. The name of any science, what it means, where the name first appeared, is geographical on the one hand, and toponymy on the other. Toponymy, the science of geographical names, is closely related to the sciences of geology, geomorphology, and hingenography, which study the structure and properties of a specific region of the planet. This research paper revealed a few etymological peculiarities of Uzbek and English toponyms through the scientists' work.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

1. Nikonov, V.A., (2011) Introduction to Топонимы. Pub.2nded.-M: Publishing LKI.
2. А. М.КомковСловарь географических названий зарубежных стран. М.. 1986
3. Nodirakhon Makhmudovna Ismatova PRINCIPLES OF TOPONYMS CLASSIFICATIONS // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №3.
4. John Everett-Heath. A brief Dictionary of World place names (2 ed.) Publisher: Oxford University Press. Published online: 2010. Current online version: 2014 e ISBN: 9780199580897.
5. Qoraev S. Топонимы. -Т.; 2006, - p. 26.
6. D.U. Ashurova, M.R.Galiyeva. Cultural Linguistics. Tashkent. 2019. p.45